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Dana E. Stewart. *The Arrow of Love: Optics, Gender, and Subjectivity in Medieval Love Poetry*. London: Bucknell University Press, 2003. Pp. 186, bibl., index. ISBN 0-8387-5480-5.

The devastating effects of Cupid's arrow and the beloved's gaze are two topoi that provided poets with seemingly infinite inspiration. In this scholarly study, Dana E. Stewart examines how medieval poets integrated philosophical optical theory in order to breathe new life into such ancient common places, and how in doing so constructed subjectivity and gender roles. In medieval lyric, Cupid's arrow itself is often metaphorically replaced with a beloved's gaze that leaves the wretched poet languishing and helpless. The two major optical theories are of the two philosophers that we would expect: Socrates and Aristotle. Socrates' theory of extramission attributed our ability to see to rays exiting our eyes; while Aristotle's was one of intromission—things are carried into our eyes when light is present. The former theory is thus, in a general sense, active, the latter passive. Other English, Greek and Arabic philosophers and physicians contributed to and expanded upon these theories, greatly influencing medieval science and poetry. The two principle theories did not always co-exist; throughout the Middle Ages, the Platonic theory ceded in popularity to the Aristotelian. It is thus interesting to note which theories the poets make use of and how, such as in the case of Dante, poets will admit to using theories contemporarily out of vogue, but still poetically effective. Stewart analyzes the gender roles poets constructed by usually attributing the active Platonic theory to the beloved, and the passive Aristotelian theory to the poet, whom receives her wounding gaze; as well as how poets attempted to redeem and defend themselves in poetry against this powerful female weapon.

Stewart organizes her study into six parts. The introduction provides an excellent overview of the philosophical perspectives, the use of visual themes in earlier poetry and the role of sight and imagination in Italian love poetry. The four central chapters respectively discuss Chrétien de Troyes' *Cligés*, the poets at the Court of Frederick II, Guido Cavalcanti, and Dante's use of optics and subjectivity in his *Rime* and *Convivio*. The epilogue briefly examines the continuation of these themes into the Renaissance in the poetry of Petrarch, Spenser and Donne.

In Stewart's examination of Chrétien's *Cligés* the discussion is limited to the passages in which Soredamors and Alexander reflect upon the effect seeing each other had on them, and Chrétien's use of Aristotle. While Soredamors initially blames her eyes as the source of her pain, she soon realizes the foolishness of the accusation, for it is she who feels love, not her eyes; Alexander, on the other hand, is not capable of accepting his fair share of the blame and plays the victim. Stewart found that Chrétien made use principally of Aristotelian optical theory at a time when Platonic theory was predominating because "he chooses metaphors that characterize the eyes as transparent,

passive entryways to the heart” (41). Furthermore, Chrétien’s portrayal of Alexander can be read as “a satirical commentary on literary lovers who blame Love or others for their condition” (48). Chrétien thus revives an ancient topos by integrating literature and science, not to mention healthy doses of intelligence and wit.

Next, we are ushered to the birthplace of the Italian poetic tradition at the court of Frederick II, which, being a centre of translation of Greek and Arabic philosophical treatises, is of particular interest. In many examples of Sicilian poetry, such as that of Giacomo da Lentini, Stewart reveals a complete juxtaposition between the lover and the beloved; the poet is often the passive languishing lover, depicted using Aristotelian theory, while the beloved actively shoots penetrating, powerful glances, adapted from Platonic theory. Da Lentini’s poetry raised difficult questions regarding optics, questions that all philosophical theses tried to answer, such as, how does the pupil manage to take in figures physically so much larger than itself. In raising such questions, da Lentini placed himself right in middle of contemporary philosophical debate.

The Sicilian poets continued the tradition of personifying the lover’s inner faculties, at times dividing the lyric “I” from the poet’s heart and eyes, etc., an elaboration not usually granted to the beloved. Stewart found that this not only serves to individualize the poet, but also to present the poet as passive and blameless. The lyric “I” never claims responsibility, rather it blames the individual faculties of working as henchmen of the lady, which leads to the old discussion regarding female subversion and will to rule. Stewart found that “by fracturing [the poet’s] subjectivity and maintaining a distance from his own mental and physical faculties, the languishing lover can disavow all responsibility for his predicament...”(67) and any consequences that may result from it. It is well known how this love poetry can often turn to insults and accusations when the lady does not return the lover’s affection. Stewart notes that a master-servant relationship dictated by the servant is “a flimsy construction” (80) indeed, especially since she is usually denied the ability to think, or even, ironically, to see. She is therefore reduced to little more than a prop, and the threat of social subversion is routed.

Cavalcanti’s use of optical theory was nearly unprecedented in its extensiveness and technical detail. He commonly utilizes Aristotelian theory when describing himself and Galeno-Platonic theory when describing his beloved’s eyes. However, Stewart argues that the theory which best describes Cavalcanti is the synthesizing and harmonizing one propounded by perspectivists, whose chief proponents include Roger Bacon and John Pecham, even though Cavalcanti’s conclusions can be quite different from theirs. Stewart goes on to apply feminist film theory to the male gaze, the results it produces in him and the repercussions of the female gaze. In romance literature up to Cavalcanti, the pattern had been for the male to revenge his anxiety by objectifying the female in an enumeration of her physical assets, while the gazing female was quickly punished for her transgression with insults and accusations of cruelty. Stewart reveals how Cavalcanti breaks from this tradition by practicing none of these habits, seeming “to embrace his

suffering and passive subservience more fully” (99) by not defusing the lady’s power. Cavalcanti, not limited by courtly etiquette, sought to reveal love’s negative aspects by playing the unavenged victim in order to warn to his readers and to urge them to seek a philosophically more profound happiness.

In her discussion of Dante, Stewart focuses on two optical passages in the *Convivio* and on “Così nel mio parlar voglio esser aspro” from the *Rime Petrose*. Like Cavalcanti, in his early verses Dante makes use of the Galeno-Platonic and Aristotelian models, only to, later, in the *Convivio*, proclaim the veracity of Aristotle, while contemporaneously asserting the poetic effectiveness scientifically outmoded ideas can convey. Thus, if Dante continues to operate Platonic metaphors, it is only for effect. Dante displays a fluent knowledge in his elaboration of optical philosophy and Stewart’s lucid argumentation makes clear just how pertinent a topic optics was at the time, as well as how conscience all the poets examined in her monograph were of integrating potential scientific fact into their analysis of love and its effects. In the poem from the *Rime Petrose*, part of a series of four about the poet’s frustration with regards to a particularly cold lady, Stewart argues that in Dante’s fantasy of being able to return the lady’s gaze, there is a metaphor for rape. She highlights past scholarship that has been uneasy in affirming this rape imagery, but asserts that to do so “is to miss the extraordinary way in which Dante implicates the dynamics of looking in this disturbing and violent fantasy of retaliation and revenge” (123).

Tracing the historical trajectory of Cupid’s arrow, Stewart aimed to prove how medieval poets transformed an ancient topos with the integration of scientific introspection. The influence of these medieval innovations resonated for centuries and Stewart concludes her study illustrating their presence and further adaptations through the span of the Renaissance in the poetry of Petrarch, Spencer and Donne. Stewart makes a valuable contribution to the study of one of the foremost topoi in medieval literature, shedding particular light on the social implications the poets, and a culture, adhered to.

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